

Decomposition Analysis of Horticulture Sector in the State of Jammu and Kashmir

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Abstract - The Northern most state of India, Jammu and Kashmir has different topographical and environmental conditions, possesses comparative advantage in the production of various horticultural products. The state offers good scope for cultivation of horticultural crops; covering a variety of temperate fruits and sub tropical fruits. An attempt has been made in this study to analyse the growth of major horticulture crops in the state over the past two decades i.e. between 1998-99 and 2017-18 and decomposition analysis has been carried out. It is found from the study that during the study period of 20 years, the area under aggregate horticulture recorded growth of 156.15 percent, while as the production and productivity of aggregate horticulture recorded a remarkable growth of 250.15 percent and 160.35 percent respectively. The decomposition analysis shows that the growth in production of aggregate horticulture, area effect accounts for 40.13 percent, yield effect accounts for 37.34 percent and interaction effect is accounts for 22.53 percent. In case of apple, the growth in production is mainly due to yield effect accounting for 70.61 percent and growth in production of walnuts is mainly due effect accounts for 54.91 percent. Almond is the only horticulture crop for which yield and interaction effect was negative, indicating the production increase was solely due to area effect accounting for 777.44 percent.

Keywords - Area, Decomposition Analysis, Growth, Horticulture, Production and Productivity.

Introduction - The Northern most state of India, Jammu and Kashmir state is predominantly an agrarian economy. The agriculture sector is gradually diversifying in favor of high-value commodities especially fruits, vegetables, livestock and fish products. The determinants for high-value commodities are markets, roads and technology absorption (Joshi, et al. (2004)¹. The state of Jammu and Kashmir has different topographical and environmental conditions, possesses comparative advantage in the production of various horticultural products. The state enjoys monopoly in the production of saffron, black zeera and some fresh fruits and dry fruits (Delicious Apple, Almonds, etc) (Lone and Sen, 2014)². In Kashmir valley, apple is the most commonly planted and commercially the most important fruit crop among all the fruits grown. Apple cultivation is profitable economic activity in the Kashmir valley as compared to other agriculture food crops (Malik, et al., 2014)³. The state offers good scope for cultivation of horticultural crops; covering a variety of temperate fruits like apple, cherry, pear, peach, plum, apricot, almond, cherry and sub tropical fruits like mango, guava, citrus litchi, phalsa and berete. Besides; mushroom, plantation crops, medicinal and aromatic plants, floriculture and vegetables are cultivated in the state (Bhat and Bhat, 2014)⁴.

The area and production of horticulture crops in the state of Jammu and Kashmir have been increasing and

the trend is projected to amplify the demand for fruits in future as evidenced by the high income elasticity of demand (Ahangar and Govindasamy, 2013)⁵. The state of Jammu and Kashmir has witnessed voluminous increase in area and production of horticulture crops over the last few decades. Over the past 20 years the area under aggregate horticulture recorded growth of 156.15 percent, while as the production and productivity of aggregate horticulture recorded a remarkable growth of 250.15 percent and 160.35 percent respectively (Govt. of J&K)⁶.

The growth in area, production and yield of major horticulture crops revealed the general pattern of growth and direction of changes in yield and area. But this analysis does not evaluate the contribution of area and yield towards the growth in production. So, it becomes compulsory to examine the sources of output growth. Therefore, to measure the relative contribution of area and yield towards the total output change with respect of individual horticulture crops and aggregate horticulture, decomposition analysis as suggested by minhas and vaidyanathan (1965)⁷ has been used. In the literature, several researchers have used this model to study growth performance of the crops {Dharke and Sharma (2010)⁸, Rehman, et al. (2011)⁹, Rather, (2014)¹⁰, Devi, et al. (2017)¹¹, Kumar and Shekhar (2017)¹².

Objectives Of The Study :

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- (i) To study the growth in area, production and yield of major horticulture crops in Jammu and Kashmir
- (ii) To carry out the decomposition analysis of major horticulture crops in the state of Jammu and Kashmir.

Research Methodology - Keeping in view the status of the research work, the data has been collected from the secondary sources. The secondary source of data have been collected from various official sources like Horticulture Statistics Division, Economic Survey of Jammu & Kashmir, Economic Review of Jammu and Kashmir, Department of Horticulture Jammu & Kashmir and Digest of Statistics Jammu and Kashmir. Further various published research papers, books, periodicals, reports, magazines, newspapers, and websites have also been used for the study. The present study covers a time period of 20 years i.e. 1998-99 to 2017-18

Statistical Analysis - The statistical techniques used in this study are Growth Rate and Decomposition Analysis.

$$(a) \text{ Growth Rate} = \frac{Y_t - Y_{t-1}}{Y_{t-1}} \times 100$$

Where, Y_t = Value of current year
 Y_{t-1} = Value of base year

(b) Decomposition Analysis - Decomposition analysis as suggested by Minhas and Vaidyanthan (1965)¹³ is used to examine the sources of output growth of horticulture sector in Jammu and Kashmir. In the decomposition analysis, the change in production is taken as the effect of three factors such as yield effect, area effect and interaction effect as follows.

$$\Delta P = AB \Delta Y + YB \Delta A + \Delta A \Delta Y$$

Change in production = Yield effect + Area effect + Interaction effect

Where, $\Delta P = PC - PB$
 $\Delta Y = YC - YB$
 $\Delta A = AC - AB$

AB, PB and YB are the area, production and yield of horticulture crops for the base year. AC, PC and YC are the area, production and yield of horticulture crops for the current year.

Results and Discussion

Table 1.1: Growth of Major Horticulture Crops in Jammu and Kashmir during the Year 2017-18 over the Year 1998-99

Growth	Apple	Pear	Walnut	Almond	Other	Total
Area	197.29	163.05	146.67	30.29	143.48	156.15
Production	237.85	338.20	338.57	150.47	267.32	250.15
Productivity	120.53	207.26	231.65	500.00	186.62	160.35

Source: Computed by Author from the Data Derived from Department of Horticulture, Jammu and Kashmir-Srinagar

The growth of various major horticulture crops in the state of Jammu and Kashmir in terms of area, production and productivity during the year 2017 -18 over the year 1998-99 is presented in table 1.1. It is obvious from the

table that, over the past 20 years the area under aggregate horticulture recorded growth of 156.15 percent, while as the production and productivity of aggregate horticulture recorded a remarkable growth of 250.15 percent and 160.35 percent respectively.

Among the various horticulture crops the highest growth in terms of area in the year 2017-18 over 1998-99 was recorded by apple (197.29 percent) followed by Pear (163.05 percent), walnut (146.67 percent) and almond (30.29 percent). In terms of production the highest growth was displayed by walnut (338.57 percent) followed by pear (338.20 percent), apple (237.85 percent) and almond (150.47 percent). In terms of productivity the highest growth was recorded by almond (500.00 percent) followed by walnut (231.65 percent), pear (207.26 percent) and apple (120.53 percent).

Decomposition Analysis - To estimate the percentage contribution of area, yield and the interaction of area and yield in increasing production of major horticulture crops in the state of Jammu and Kashmir, a decomposition analysis was carried out and presented in table 1.2 for a time period of 20 years (1998-99 to 2017-18).

Table 1.2 (see in next page)

The decomposition analysis presented in table 1.2 clearly shows that the growth in production of aggregate horticulture, all the three effects are positive. The table further reveals that the area and yield effects have more or less equal contribution to total change in output growth, area effect accounting for 40.13 percent, yield effect accounting for 37.34 percent and interaction effect is accounting for 22.53 percent.

It is obvious from the table that in case of apple, all the three effects are positive, but the growth in production is mainly due to yield effect accounting for 70.61 percent, area and interaction effects have same contribution to total change in output growth of apples accounting for 14.90 percent and 14.49 percent respectively.

Furthermore, it is clear from the table that the growth in production of walnuts is mainly due to increase in area and area effect accounts for 54.91 percent where as yield and interaction effects accounts for 19.46 percent and 25.61 percent respectively. Almond is the only horticulture crop for which yield and interaction effect was negative, indicating the production increase was solely due to area effect accounting for 777.44 percent. In case of other fruits, area effect accounts for 51.63 percent whereas yield and interaction effects accounts for 25.92 and 22.45 percent.

Conclusion - The state of Jammu and Kashmir has witnessed voluminous increase in area and production of horticulture crops over the last few decades. Over the past 20 years the area under aggregate horticulture recorded growth of 156.15 percent, while as the production and productivity of aggregate horticulture recorded a remarkable growth of 250.15 percent and 160.35 percent respectively. Among the various horticulture crops the highest growth in terms of area was recorded by apple (197.29 percent)

followed by Pear (163.05 percent), in terms of production the highest growth was displayed by walnut (338.57 percent) followed by pear (338.20 percent) and in terms of productivity the highest growth was recorded by almond (500.00 percent) followed by walnut (231.65 percent), pear (207.26 percent) and apple (120.53 percent).

The decomposition analysis shows that the growth in production of aggregate horticulture, area effect accounts for 40.13 percent, yield effect accounts for 37.34 percent and interaction effect is accounts for 22.53 percent. In case of apple, the growth in production is mainly due to yield effect accounting for 70.61 percent and growth in production of walnuts is mainly due effect accounts for 54.91 percent. Almond is the only horticulture crop for which yield and interaction effect was negative, indicating the production increase was solely due to area effect accounting for 777.44 percent.

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Table 1.2: Decomposition Analysis of Growth in Production of Major Horticulture Crops in Jammu and Kashmir (1998-99 to 2017-18)

Crops	Aspects	Differential Production (ΔP)	Area Effect (ΔA)	Yield Effect (ΔY)	Interaction Effect ($\Delta A \Delta Y$)
Apple	Actual	1090814	162505.2	770212.5	158096.25
	Percentage	100	14.90	70.61	14.49
Pear	Actual	62982.24	28392	16689.24	17901
	Percentage	100	45.08	26.50	28.42
Walnut	Actual	194556	106833.6	37867.77	49854.69
	Percentage	100	54.91	19.46	25.62
Almond	Actual	4461.54	34685.84	-6044.86	-24179.44
	Percentage	100	777.44	-135.49	-541.95
Others	Actual	105828.7	54643.98	27427.3	23757.45
	Percentage	100	51.63	25.92	22.45
Total	Actual	1459215	585614.7	544800	328800
	Percentage	100	40.13	37.34	22.53

Source: Computed by Author from the Data Derived from Department of Horticulture, Jammu and Kashmir-Srinagar